

The Aquatic Toxicity of Lysol Toilet Bowl Cleaner on *Raphanus sativus* Germination

Sabrina Bialy

Western Albemarle High School/Piedmont Virginia Community College

BIO 107/615: Biology of the Environment

Ms. Dawn Tinder

15 February 2024

The Impact of Aquatic Toxicity on *Raphanus sativus* Germination

A potential source, or contaminant, of irrigation water is sewage. Some believe it is beneficial to reuse this water; however, sewage water is full of contaminants that can negatively affect the growth and germination rates of different plants. A previous study has shown that irrigation of sunflowers with water contaminated by household cleaning products at high concentrations has had negative effects on plant germination and growth and should be avoided (Heidari, 2013). Determining the effect on seed germination will allow a better understanding of why it is environmentally detrimental to expose seeds to water with contaminants from toxic household cleaners, such as Lysol toilet bowl cleaner. Although products like this are frequently used within households, it is important to understand the environmental implications, and determine the effect on the growth of vegetation and aquatic plants. In this experiment, the effect of a potential water contaminant, Lysol toilet bowl cleaner, will be tested in different concentrations to determine the impact it has on the germination rate of radish seeds (*Raphanus sativus*). *R. sativus* seeds were chosen for this study due to the speed at which they typically germinate, making observations easier to make during data collection. Lysol toilet bowl cleaner is known to have chemicals in it that have negative impacts on plants that are exposed to it. This negative impact is regarding not only growth but also germination rate. According to EWG (n.d.), the major active ingredient in Lysol toilet bowl cleaner is hydrochloric acid, a corrosive substance that is damaging to human skin and eyes. The low pH of the hydrochloric acid, among other chemicals, will likely have a negative impact on the germination of the seeds. It is hypothesized that during an acute exposure of 12 days, a 20% concentration of the cleaner will result in an IC_{50} response of the *R. sativus* seeds failing to germinate (IC_{50} - the concentration that causes a lethal response within 50% of the test population).

Materials and Methods

This experiment was conducted at Western Albemarle High School in Crozet, Virginia in the fall of 2023. 6 different concentrations of Lysol toilet bowl cleaner were used in order to test the aquatic toxicity of the cleaning product. 60 seeds total were used, 10 seeds were enclosed within a ziploc bag and were folded between a paper towel that had absorbed 10 ml of the varying concentrations; 0% (control), 1.25%, 2.5%, 5%, 10%, and 20%. The duration of the experiment took 12 days, with observations made on days 4, 5, 8, and 12. On days 4, 5, and 8, the germination rate for each concentration was observed and recorded. On day 12, each seedling that had germinated within each concentration was measured in length (from root to tip) and the data was averaged and recorded in centimeters.

Results

The percent of seeds germinated and average seedling length under the different concentrations of Lysol toilet bowl cleaner has been determined from the results. Within the control group (0% concentration), all 10 seeds had germinated by day 8. By day 12, 3 seeds from the 1.25% concentration had germinated, and only 1 from the 2.5%. None of the other concentrations experienced any growth. The IC_{50} was determined to be approximately 1.75% concentration (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. The percent of seeds germinated found within each concentration. IC_{50} was determined to be approximately 1.75%.

Of the germinated seeds, all were measured in length (centimeters) from root to tip and recorded. (See Table 1).

Table 1. Shows the growth of Radish seeds after 12 days of exposure to Lysol Toilet bowl Cleaner.

Concentration (%)	Seed #1 (cm)	Seed #2 (cm)	Seed #3 (cm)	Seed #4 (cm)	Seed #5 (cm)	Average length of seedling (cm)
0.00	2	4	1.5	4	3	2.9
1.25	1	0.5	0.25	0	0	0.6
2.50	0.25	0	0	0	0	0.25
5.00	0	0	0	0	0	0
10.00	0	0	0	0	0	0
20.00	0	0	0	0	0	0

The average seedling length within the control group was 2.9 cm. While the average seedling lengths for the 1.25% concentration was 0.6 cm, and was 0.25 cm for 2.5%. (See Figure 2).

Figure 2. The average length of the seedlings (in cm) found within each concentration.

Discussion

The results indicate that Lysol toilet bowl cleaner is harmful to not only germination rates within plant species but also seedling length. Contrary to the original hypothesis that the IC_{50} would be at a concentration of 20%, it was determined to be at a much lower level, approximately 1.75%. The IC_{50} in the original hypothesis was an underestimate, and Lysol is in fact more detrimental to growth and reproduction rates within *R. sativus* seeds than originally anticipated. This trend in negative germination rates as concentration rates increase can likely be attributed to the numerous hazardous chemicals found in this household product, such as hydrochloric acid, benzenesulfonic acid, and alcohol ethoxylates. Consumption of alcohol while pregnant is known

to negatively impact fetal development. Hence, why would alcohol affect reproduction and growth any differently for plants? Additionally, hydrochloric acid (HCL) has a pH of 1.1, while optimal pH levels for seed germination range between 6.5 and 7.5. Very acidic soils can reduce the amount of micro- and macronutrients available to plants (Lovejoy, 2012). Therefore, the acidic conditions and exposure to alcohol negatively impact the conditions under which seedling germination occurs, explaining the decline in germination rate and growth as the concentration rate of Lysol toilet bowl cleaner increased.

Having analyzed the results, moving forward, another experiment could be conducted similarly, but with a different household cleaner that contains no alcohol, acids, or toxic ingredients of any sort. For example, it would be interesting to see the effects on growth and rate of germination from Dr. Bronner's pure castile soap, which claims it is made with all organic ingredients. The differences that would be observed could serve to emphasize the toxicity of Lysol toilet bowl cleaner, showing the importance of looking at the ingredients in the products used daily within many households worldwide. Many household cleaners, such as Lysol toilet bowl cleaner, have shown to disrupt natural processes within the surrounding environment. Along with a negative environmental impact, some ingredients contain allergens and carcinogens which can negatively impact human health. By finding cleaners with safer ingredients, consumers can protect themselves, their families, and the environment. Furthermore, consumer purchasing power, through the purchase of environmentally safe products, would influence policies and regulations regarding chemical use and waste management. This would promote better environmental protection through improved industry practices and societal norms - leading the world to a more sustainable future.

References

EWG. (n.d.) *Lysol Toilet Bowl Cleaner Rating*. EWG's Guide to Healthy Cleaning. Retrieved November 16, 2023, from

<https://www.ewg.org/guides/cleaners/1192-LYSOLToiletBowlCleanerPower/>

Heidari, H. (2013). Effect of Irrigation with Contaminated Water by Cloth Detergent on Seed Germination Traits and Early Growth of Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.). *Notulae*

Scientia Biologicae, 5(1), 86–89. <https://doi.org/10.15835/nsb519003>

Lovejoy, R. (2012, October 29). How Does pH Affect Plants? Weekand.

<https://www.weekand.com/home-garden/article/ph-affect-plants-18053224.php>